

Effects of Conflict Management Strategies on Organizational Performance: A Case of the National Empowerment Network of People Living With Hiv/Aids in Kenya

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Abstract:

This study aimed to establish the importance of proper selection and implementation of conflict management strategies in an organization while looking at the capacity building as a cause of conflict. The study recognizes the value of undertaking capacity building exercises but notes that it can also lead to conflict that may damage an organization's ability to perform. In the study, therefore, the effects of conflict management strategies on organizational performance were examined using the National Empowerment Network of People Living with HIV/AIDS in Kenya as a case study. A total of 49 respondents comprising NEPHAK employees, volunteers and board of directors were selected through the use of stratified random sampling technique. Structured questionnaires were used to collect data, which was analyzed through descriptive statistics. Spearman Correlation statistics was employed to determine the empirical test results and found a significantly positive relationship between organizational performance and conflict management strategies of collaborating, compromising and accommodating while competing and avoiding strategies reflected a negative effect on performance. The study concluded that conflict is inevitable and it could either have a positive or negative effect on performance depending on the conflict management methods adopted by the organization. The study, therefore, concludes that integrative bargaining methods of collaborating, compromising and accommodating were the most selected strategies as these present positive effects on the overall organizational performance and therefore recommends adoption of integrative methods.

Keywords: Conflict; Conflict Management; Organization; Organizational Performance

1. Introduction

According to Flaherty, (2015), conflict refers to the perceived incompatibilities resulting from some form of interference or opposition. Dzurgha, (2006) also defines conflict as a social problem in which two or more persons, families, parties, communities, or districts are in disagreement with each other. Ajike et al., (2015) noted that conflict in an employment relationship has been an issue of continuing interest and debate and is a common occurrence in organizational life. According to Darling and Walker, (2007), organizations require the human touch to drive various technologies and departments that enhance interaction between customers and workers occupying different levels of the organizational structure. As these factors combine, and as the human element interacts with a given organization, conflict is inevitable, and performance is affected either positively or negatively depending on the degree of conflict and how it is managed. Conflict in an organization, therefore, depends on the degree with which interests, values, and goals of individuals are met and may arise due to anger, mistrust or personality clashes (Darling and Walker, 2007). Azamosa, (2004) observed that conflict involves the total range of behaviors and attitudes that are in conflict between owners and managers on the one hand, and working people on the other. Classical organization theorists believed that conflict produced inefficiency and was therefore undesirable, detrimental to the organization and should be eliminated or at least minimized (Ajike et al., 2015). Perceptions about conflict changed with the emergence of social systems and open system theory (Algert and Watson, 2002; Ajike et al., 2015). According to the social system theories, conflict is one of the central forms of interaction. Ajike et al., (2015), also stated that Emile Durkheim supported this view that conflict is normal and functional because it brings about positive changes in an organization, which may, in turn, improve performance.

Conflict, however, becomes negative if it is not well managed and allowed to reach a dysfunctional stage. Effective conflict management is therefore essential for any organization to achieve its goals and maintain productivity for effective organizational performance. Salami, (2009) asserts that conflict resolution strategies adopted in resolving conflicts between workers and management may influence the workers' attitude regarding

work and the organization. It is therefore important to examine the effects of the different conflict management strategies on the attitudes of workers. This is because a worker who has experienced work-place frustration or suffered organizational injustice arising from the way management-worker conflicts were resolved may engage in counterproductive work activities such as character assassination, spreading negative rumours, sabotaging, turnover, and withholding organizational citizenship behaviour (OCB) (Ogungbamila, (2006); Salami, (2009). The study focused on the National Empowerment Network of People living with HIV/AIDS in Kenya (NEPHAK) being an institution comprising the human element as part of its resources. Disagreements over allocation and management of resources resulting from structural changes, alterations to the organization's strategic direction and changes in operations triggered conflict within the organization following a capacity building exercise aimed at improving the organization's operations. Selecting appropriate strategies to manage this conflict was therefore critical. According to Longe, (2015), the task of management is not to suppress or resolve all conflicts, but to manage them in order to enhance and not to detract from organizational performance. The study, therefore, explored organizational conflict and how the strategies used to manage conflict could enhance performance at NEPHAK.

Five conflict management strategies of collaborating, compromising, accommodating, avoiding, and competing have been universally adopted by conflicting parties, depending on the level of the win/lose orientation of the parties involved (Ogungbamila, 2006; Salami, 2009). A win/lose orientation determines which of the conflict management strategies will be applied to a specific conflict situation based on two dimensions of behavior: assertiveness and cooperativeness. White, (2016) indicates that when dealing with conflict, techniques that work best for a particular situation should be selected rather than sticking to an approach that seems most comfortable. The conflict Mode Instrument (TKI) developed by Thomas-Kilmann in 1976 is widely used to decide the best approach to use. When adapting a particular strategy, it is important to consider the people involved, the organization's culture, the ultimate goal and the nature of the specific conflict (White, 2016). In addition to the five conflict management strategies proposed in Thomas-Kilmann's TKI mode that will be discussed in this study, conflict can also be resolved through joint consultation, mediation, arbitration, conciliation and collective bargaining. McShane and Von Glinow (2001) as cited in Salami, (2009) introduced the dimension of assertiveness-cooperativeness and win-win and win-loss orientation along the continuum in describing each of the five conflicts resolution strategies. These strategies provide solutions to conflict management as universal and can be interchanged and combined in an effort to adapt to specific regional influences and practices.

1.1 Research Objectives

The general objective of the study was to determine the effect of conflict management strategies on the organizational performance of the National Empowerment Network of People living with HIV/AIDS in Kenya. Specific objectives were to:

- Establish the effect of collaborating strategy on the performance of the National Empowerment Network of People living with HIV/AIDS in Kenya;
- Determine the effect of compromising strategy on the performance of the National Empowerment Network of People living with HIV/AIDS in Kenya;
- Establish the effect of accommodating strategy on the performance of the National Empowerment Network of People living with HIV/AIDS in Kenya;
- Explore the effect of competing strategy on the performance of the National Empowerment Network of People living with HIV/AIDS in Kenya; and
- Determine the effect of avoiding strategy on the performance of the National Empowerment Network of People living with HIV/AIDS in Kenya.

1.2 Research Hypotheses

The research was tested on the following null hypotheses:

H₀₁. Collaborating strategy has no significant effect on the performance of the National Empowerment Network of People living with HIV/AIDS in Kenya

- H0₂. Compromising strategy has no significant effect on the performance of the National Empowerment Network of People living with HIV/AIDS in Kenya
- H0₃. Accommodating strategy has no significant effect on the performance of the National Empowerment Network of People living with HIV/AIDS in Kenya
- H0₄. Competing strategy has no significant effect on the performance of the National Empowerment Network of People living with HIV/AIDS in Kenya
- H0₅. Avoiding strategy has no significant effect on the performance of the National Empowerment Network of People living with HIV/AIDS in Kenya

2. Literature Review

This section reviewed existing literature and documentation on conflict management strategies and their effect on organizational performance. Consideration was given to two theories of conflict management, and these were compared to empirical studies that have been carried out by several researchers. A conceptual framework based on the review was further laid out.

Theoretical Framework

A theoretical framework introduces and explains the existence of a research problem and provides explanations about the phenomenon (Marriam, 2001). Theories presented in the theoretical framework contain a set of assumptions drawn from arguments that are logically connected and can be proven or supported using existing empirical literature that form the foundations of the study. This study will be anchored on contingency theory and organizational learning theory.

Organizational Learning Theory

Scott, (2011) states that learning is both a cognitive and a behavioral process where new insights lead to new behavior. She adds that learning is increasingly viewed as an active, social, and dynamic process, facilitated by people reflecting and acting together. Accordingly, the quality of learning interactions among people and communities is a core resource that must be nurtured and maintained. From her empirical research, Scott, (2011) also noted that learning in organizations is a multi-level pursuit, occurring through individuals, amongst groups and communities and embedded through routines, norms, and other organizational features. Argote, (2013) noted that, although researchers have debated whether organizational learning should be termed as a change in cognition or in behavior that debate has declined. Frost, (2010), suggests that organizations should design conflict management strategies that enhance organizational learning as this improves the effectiveness of an organization leading to good performance. Conflict management strategies should, therefore, be designed to enhance critical and innovative thinking to the learning process of diagnosis and intervention in the right problems (Rahim, 2002). Tompkins, (1995); Rahim, (2007) explain that the organizational learning theory shows how various organizations could set their own conflict management structures and allows an organization to make an inquiry to the conflict based on their preferred mode of operation. This complex mechanism often results in storage of interpretations of past events and not the events themselves. Frost, (2010), points out the argument by Argyris and Schon, (1996), who emphasized that this interaction often goes well beyond defined organizational rules and procedures, which are based on two, often conflicting modes of operation. The espoused theory defines the formalized part of the organization. It assumes that every firm tends to have various instructions regarding the way employees should conduct themselves in order to carry out their jobs. This includes problem-solving for which instructions are often specific and narrow in focus, confining the individual to a set path. Scott, (2011) added that when espousing an alternative perspective, as stated by Hedberg (1981):

“Although organizational learning occurs through individuals, it would be a mistake to conclude that organizational learning is nothing but the cumulative result of their members’ learning. Organizations do not have brains, but they have cognitive systems and memories. Members come and go, and leadership changes, but organizations’ memories preserve certain behavior, mental maps, norms and values over time.”

Going by Hedberg’s argument, the organizational learning theory, therefore, assumes that past experiences can be used in organizations either as a best practice of lessons learned. As such, organizations can store information about situations where specific conflict management strategies worked well to improve its performance, which

can be adopted in future whenever similar situations arise. Alternatively, organizations can avoid using strategies that negatively affected its operations based on information that exists in its cognitive systems. Theory-in-use, as compared to espoused theory, is the actual way things are done and refers to the loose, flowing, and social way that employees solve problems and learn. This assumes that individuals often rely on interaction and brainstorming to solve a problem and will rarely follow the espoused theory (Frost, 2010). Given this approach, attitudes and behaviour at the workplace resulting from how conflict is managed can be influenced greatly by the level of employee involvement in decision making and problem-solving. When learning takes place in the workplace, employees are able to adopt best strategies that positively influence performance, and this determines the extent to which organizational objectives are attained.

Contingency Theory of Conflict Management

Schoech, (2006) termed contingency as a relationship between two phenomena and notes that if one phenomenon exists, then a conclusion can be drawn about another phenomenon. This theory tries to explain how different conditions influence outcomes in an organization. It then becomes necessary to study situations within an organization that warrants implementation of appropriate conflict management strategies that contribute to the organization's stability and overall growth. Derr, (1975) as cited in Agwu, (2013), opined that contingency theory is one of the conceptual tools used for managing organizational conflicts. He stated that there are three major conflict management approaches from which managers can draw to formulate an appropriate approach for resolving a dispute. These include collaboration, bargaining and power play. Dür and Mateo (2010) also add to this discussion concept of integrative and distributive bargaining approaches to manage conflict. The conflict management paradigm according to Derr, (1975), indicated that collaboration involves allowing differences to materialize between conflicting parties than working on the problems until a commonly acceptable solution is attained. This approach assumes that people will be motivated to expend time and energy for such problem-solving activities. Bargaining, on the other hand, assumes that neither party will emerge satisfied from a confrontation, but that both, through negotiation, can get something they did not have at the beginning, or more of something they need, usually by giving up something of lesser importance. One party generally wins more than the other by the skillful use of tactical trades and can get the maximum possible from the other side (Agwu, 2013). This can be related to the compromise strategy which is most commonly used when an individual's goals are moderately important, but disputing parties with equal power are committed to mutually exclusive goals (White, 2016). The essence of contingency theory is that best practices depend on the contingencies of the situation. Contingency theorists try to identify and measure the conditions under which things will likely occur. This theory is therefore applicable for organizations when determining the best and most relevant conflict management strategy to use since each strategy choice would have different outcomes and effects on organizational performance. Donaldson, (2008) notes that conflict management depends on attitudes, understanding, and perceptions held by disputing parties, which greatly relies on the individual needs and interests. Further, as this theory proposes, best practices can be used as a basis for selection of conflict management strategies while putting into consideration positive outcomes in the achievement of organizational goals and objective, and in turn, improved or effective performance.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework presented in Figure 1 represents five conflict management strategies and organizational performance as the variables that will support this study. In this study, organizational performance will be viewed as the dependent variable. The independent variables include collaborating, compromising, accommodating, competing and avoiding conflict management strategies developed by Thomas-Kilmann in 1976:

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Empirical Review

2.1 Conflict Management Strategies

Five conflict management strategies of collaborating, compromising, accommodating, avoiding, and competing have been universally adopted by conflicting parties, depending on the level of the win/lose orientation of the parties involved (Ogunbamila, 2006; Salami, 2009). A win/lose orientation determines which of the conflict management strategies will be applied to a specific conflict situation based on two dimensions of behaviour: assertiveness and cooperativeness. White, (2016) indicates that when dealing with conflict, techniques that work best for a particular situation should be selected rather than sticking to an approach that seems most comfortable. The conflict Mode Instrument (TKI) developed by Thomas-Kilmann in 1976 is widely used to decide the best approach to use. When adapting a particular strategy, it is important to consider the people involved, the organization's culture, the ultimate goal and the nature of the specific conflict (White, 2016). In addition to the five conflict management strategies proposed in Thomas-Kilmann's TKI mode that will be discussed in this study, conflict can also be resolved through joint consultation, mediation, arbitration, conciliation and collective bargaining. McShane and Von Glinow (2001) as cited in Salami, (2009) introduced the dimension of assertiveness-cooperativeness and win-win and win-loss orientation along the continuum in describing each of the five conflicts resolution strategies. These strategies provide solutions to conflict management as universal and can be interchanged and combined in an effort to adapt to specific regional influences and practices.

2.1.1 Collaborating strategy

Collaborating is usually high on both assertiveness and cooperativeness, often described as the win-win scenario since both sides creatively work towards achieving the goals and desired outcomes of all parties

involved. When collaborating, an individual attempts to work with the other person to find a solution that fully satisfies the concerns of both CPP Inc. (2010). Existing literature presents arguments by researchers who support the use of collaborating as a conflict management strategy. Salami, (2009) agrees that collaborating is an appropriate strategy especially when the concerns are complex and creative or novel synthesis of ideas is required. Usually, the goals of involved parties are compatible since both parties place more importance on the working relationship and therefore this is characterized by fair play. Salami, (2009) argues that collaborating may create positive work behaviour and attitudes of the parties in conflict. The collaboration strategy involves information sharing among parties and clarifies issues on the point of conflict with the other party so as to reach a solution acceptable to both parties (Salami, 2009). This strategy takes a win-win approach to conflict management and is based on the belief that it is possible to come up with a solution that satisfies the concerns and meets the needs of all parties (White, 2006).

2.1.2 Compromising strategy

Compromising, integrative bargaining or trading is characterized by moderate levels of both assertiveness and cooperativeness and produces suboptimal results. Rees, (2014) notes that this strategy is useful when the goals of both sides are of equal importance, when both sides have equal power, or when it is necessary to find a temporary, timely solution. Compromising might mean splitting the difference, exchanging concessions, or seeking a quick middle-ground position. Ngu, (2008) notes that in situations where compromising is used as a strategy to manage conflict, parties involved have equal power to influence outcomes of the resolution as both parties seek to find a quick middle-ground position to the issue. Compromise rates low on assertiveness and high on cooperativeness (Salami, (2009). This strategy may, therefore, result in positive work behaviour and attitudes.

2.1.3 Accommodating strategy

The accommodating, smoothing or obliging conflict management strategy reflects a high degree of cooperativeness and self-sacrifice (Rees, 2014). The accommodating strategy involves avoiding conflict and usually rates low on assertiveness and high on cooperativeness, thus de-emphasizes differences and highlights points common to both parties (Ogunbamila, 2006). This strategy also results in positive work behaviour and attitudes that encourage consideration of each other's interests and needs and further encourages sharing among the workforce. Performance thus becomes effective since all parties work cohesively while preserving future work relationships. White, (2016) further noted that when the long-term objective is more important than winning, the accommodating strategy can be used. This strategy is also appropriate to use when the intention is to let the other party learn from their mistakes or when one realizes they were actually wrong. Rees (2014) agrees that this strategy creates harmonious working conditions that promote organizational performance; however, this can be damaging to work relationships as it may lead to decisions that sacrifice its principles. Ngu, (2008) therefore opines that if the assertion is of importance, and the situation needs to be addressed urgently, then this strategy may be avoided.

2.1.4 Competing strategy

Dür and Mateo (2010) compare the competing strategy to a distributive bargaining approach in negotiations. This strategy, as opined by CPP, Inc, (2010), is usually associated with power and force where one party is mostly highly assertive as they seek to reach their preferred outcomes at the expense of other individuals and are unwilling to cooperate with other parties in the conflict situation. Dür and Mateo (2010) indicate that in situations where resources are scarce or limited, and the goals of conflicting parties are incompatible, they tend to lean toward competing strategies to resolve the conflict. This approach, according to White, (2016) is mostly used when the focus is on pursuing one's goals at the expense of others. Salami, (2009) further states that this approach may be appropriate when quick, decisive action is needed such as during emergencies. It can also be used to confront unpopular actions such as urgent cost-cutting, more so when cooperation is extremely low, and the persistence of satisfying personal interests is high.

2.1.5 Avoiding strategy

White, (2016) noted that this strategy involves staying away from conflict instead of addressing the issue and is highly characterized by unassertive and uncooperative parties. This strategy has the tendency to prompt

counterproductive work behaviour which affects performance (Alper et al. 2000; Meyer, 2004; Ogungbamila, 2006; Salami 2009). White, (2016) further indicates that avoiding may cause frustration and lack of self-respect to the parties being avoided and in some instances, the problem is likely to worsen and damage the relationship between parties in conflict unless it is resolved. Ogungbamila, (2006) proposes that avoiding strategy may be relevant when the potential for disruption or damage to the relationship is more significant than the benefits of resolving the conflict. Avoiding is therefore used to provide short-term solutions for evading confrontation, particularly when doing so is an appropriate course of action and is a viable option in situations where silence is the best option (Salami, 2009).

2.2 Organizational Performance

Organizational performance is an important construct in industrial and organizational psychology (Kappagoda et al., 2014). Murphy (1989) as cited in Kappagoda et al., (2014) argues that performance definitions should focus on behaviour rather than outcomes because if the managers focus only the employees' outcomes, employees will find the easiest way to achieve the outcomes without considering another important behaviour. Borman and Schmit in 1997 defined organizational performance as behaviour or activities concerned with the organization's goals and objectives. Similarly, Campbell, McHenry, and Wise in 1990 defined performance as the observable behaviour that people do in their jobs that are relevant to the goals of the organization (Kappagoda et al., 2014). Organizational performance can be affected either positively or negatively owing to various factors. If managed efficiently, these factors can be effective in enhancing positive work performance, on the other hand, if mismanaged or undermanaged, then organizational performance may be adversely affected.

Researchers have found that self-confident employees are usually good performers. According to this explanation, if the employees have high self-efficacy, they believe they can succeed. As a result, they put more effort on the given task. When employees try harder to succeed, they generally perform better. It means that self-efficacy correlates with performance (Bandura, 2000; Kappagoda et al., 2014). Hopeful employees are more effective than the low hopeful employees. According to Bandura (2000); Kappagoda et al., (2014), self-efficacious and hopeful employees perform better because these employees accept challenges and put more efforts to achieve goals owing to their high efficacy. Management teams should bear this in mind when designing conflict management strategies and consider involving their employees in the process. Involving them would, in turn, influence their behaviour and attitudes towards the organization as this builds their self-confidence and optimism towards their work. Youssef and Luthans (2007) reported a positive relationship between optimism and employee performance. Similar results were found by Seligman (1998) who agrees with this argument noting that optimism is positively and significantly correlated with the performance of insurance sales agents. Optimism at work can be characterized by highly cooperative workers who are willing to innovatively find ways to become productive at work. Work attitudes also play an important role in the achievement of organizational goals. Work attitudes can be defined as an individual's general attitude and morale towards his or her job and the organization. Wei and Chu (2008) found that work attitude has a positive relationship with an organizational performance from their survey conducted on employees in the financial service industry. Kappagoda, (2013) also found similar results in his study of the Sri Lankan banking sector. According to his research, he found a significant positive relationship between work attitudes and organizational performance. In his research, he was able to ascertain that work attitudes considerably explain the variance in the work performance of the non-managerial employees in the banking sector.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Research design, Population and Sampling Technique

In this study, questionnaires were used to collect data. A descriptive survey design was used to collect detailed and factual information as it utilizes a questionnaire as a tool for collecting data and validate variables of the study. The target population for this study comprised the NEPHAK board of directors, top management staff, non-management staff and volunteers from Nairobi, Meru, Mombasa, Nyeri, Kisumu, Nakuru and Kakamega Counties. This study adopted the stratified random sampling method that divided the target population into two

strata on the basis of their influence in decision making. Respondents from the non-management staff and volunteers were randomly picked to participate in the research. A total of 49 respondents were selected to participate in the study, accounting for 30% of the total population (Copper and Schindler, 2010).

3.2 Data Collection

In this study, primary and secondary data was collected using descriptive research methods. Data collected from this study recorded the historical development of conflict management strategies by recognizing different conflict management strategies that NEPHAK can use in future as a result of the capacity building process. Primary data was collected directly from the selected sample using formalized questionnaires containing structured questions that were analyzed statistically. The structured questions were used to limit respondents to given variables that are of interest to the study (Copper and Schindler, 2010). The findings were validated to provide objective, unbiased results while assessing the respondents’ opinions to conflict and conflict management strategies. Secondary data was collected from journal articles, book sections, the internet, reports from various sources.

3.3 Data Analysis

Direct interpretation of both primary and secondary data collection methods and sources were analyzed through descriptive statistics including means and standard deviation, inferential statistics, percentages, and frequencies using multiple regression and Spearman's correlation coefficients. The regression and Spearman correlation matrices were used to test the hypotheses. The significance of the regression model was determined at 95% confidence interval and 5% level of significance that included an analysis of variance (ANOVA). ANOVA was used since it makes use of F-test to test the joint significance of all coefficients and T-test to test the significance of individual coefficients (Mugenda and Mugenda, 2011).

4. Research Findings

According to Mugenda and Mugenda (2011), a response rate of 50% is adequate for data analysis and reporting, and a response rate of 70% is considered excellent. The study targeted sample size of 49 respondents comprising three board members, ten representatives from the secretariat including both management and non-management staff, and 41 volunteers who assist with implementing NEPHAK projects. Out of the 49 targeted respondents, 41 responded to the administered questionnaires giving a response rate of 83.7%, which provides a satisfactory basis to draw conclusions as shown in table 1.

Table 1: Response Rate

	Questionnaires Administered	Questionnaires filled and returned	Response rate
Board of Directors	3	3	100%
Management staff	2	2	100%
Non-management staff	3	3	100%
Volunteers	41	33	80.5%
Total	49	41	83.7%

Source: The Study, 2018

4.1 Demographic Findings

The findings presented indicated that majority of the participants based on ranks are non-management personnel with a representation of 87.8% which includes the volunteers who form the majority and non-management staff. Participants representing top-ranking decision makers in the organization included board of directors and management staff constituted a 12.2% representation of respondents from the organization’s management cadre. The study also established that 78.1% of the respondents have worked with NEPHAK between 3-5 years or more than ten years. This, therefore, implies that the respondents had adequately reliable information to contribute to the study. According to Longe (2015), the organizational tenure of respondents is a good way to test the reliability of information given to determine the effect of conflict management on organizational performance. The study found that 34.1% of the respondents had attained a bachelor’s degree. A further, 34.1% of the respondents indicated that they held a diploma or higher diploma and 24.4% indicated they reached college level. The study also found that 7.3% of the respondents hold a master’s degree. Kombo and Trump

(2006), indicate that a respondents' level of education is important as it determines the credibility of their response to a particular study.

4.2 Descriptive Analysis

Collaborating Strategy

Findings presented in Table 2 established that implementing the collaborating strategy increases work relationships that lead to improved organizational productivity organization as shown by the mean of 4.39 (sd=0.63). In addition, the majority of the respondents strongly agreed that implementing the collaborating strategy encourages information sharing within the organization that enables the organization to achieve its goals and objectives as shown by the mean of 4.61 (sd=0.49). The respondents also agree that collaborating with all stakeholders particularly staff boosts their morale thus leading to high staff retention as shown by the mean of 4.17 (sd=0.50) and that this strategy encourages inclusivity and recognition of the team's capabilities and gives a sense of company ownership that boosts performance as shown by the mean of 4.27 (sd=0.55). The findings also revealed that implementing the collaborating strategy would improve the performance at NEPHAK as shown by the mean of 4.51. In his study on the impact of workplace conflict management on the performance of the Nigerian manufacturing firm, Longe (2015) found that strategies that take more of a collective bargaining approach such as the collaborating strategy were found to be the most important and effective conflict management strategies to organizations.

Table 2: Means and Standard Deviations on Collaborating Strategy

Statement	Sample Size	Mean	Standard Deviation
Increases work relationships and productivity	41	4.39	0.63
Encourages information sharing and achieving organizational objectives	41	4.61	0.49
Boosts staff moral promoting high staff retention	41	4.17	0.50
Encourages inclusivity and recognition of the team's capabilities	41	4.27	0.55
Leads to improve the performance of NEPHAK	41	4.51	0.64

Compromising Strategy

Table 3 presents findings indicating that compromising strategy helps organizations find a quick middle ground that helps maintain productivity in the organization as shown by the mean of 3.51 (sd=0.51). 65.9% of the respondents also agree that the compromising strategy encourages equal sharing of power among parties involved, which encourages an all-inclusive decision-making process thus building organizational conflict management skills as shown by the mean of 4.00 (sd=0.59) and a majority of the respondents agree that the compromising strategy would improve the performance of NEPHAK if well implemented as represented by the mean of 4.00. Rees (2014) agrees with these findings, noting that the compromising strategy is useful when the goals of both parties are of equal importance, when both sides have equal power, or when it is necessary to find a temporary, timely solution to the conflict situation.

Table 3: Means and Standard Deviations on Compromising Strategy

Statement	Sample Size	Mean	Standard Deviation
Organizations find a quick middle ground	41	3.51	0.51
Encourages equal sharing of power, boosts staff morale and builds the organizational conflict management skills	41	4.00	0.59
Would improve the performance of NEPHAK	41	4.00	0.63

Source: The Study, 2018

Accommodating Strategy

As indicated in Table 4, the majority of the respondents agree that organizations that adopt this strategy usually preserve future work relationships as shown by the mean of 3.71 (sd=0.46). From the findings, 65.9% of the respondents opined that the self-sacrificing element associated with adopting the accommodating strategy to manage organizational conflict results in positive performance as shown by the mean of 3.66 (sd=0.48) and 63.4% of the responses being neutral that employees in organizations that adopt the accommodating conflict management strategy usually make good decisions as shown by the mean of 3.63 (sd=0.49). Majority of the respondents also agreed that proper implementation of the accommodating strategy would improve the performance of NEPHAK as shown by the mean of 3.90.

Table 4: Means and Standard Deviations on Accommodating Strategy

Statement	Sample Size	Mean	Standard Deviation
Preserves future work relationships	41	3.71	0.46
The self-sacrificing element associated with this strategy results in positive performance	41	3.66	0.48
Enables employees to make good decisions	41	3.63	0.49
Would improve the performance of NEPHAK	41	3.90	0.63

Source: The Study, 2018

Competing Strategy

Results shown in Table 5 indicate that the competing strategy would improve the performance of NEPHAK. Majority of the respondents disagree that the power dominance characterized by the competing strategy aimed at coercing others to perform good for improving performance in an organization a shown by the mean of 2.07 (sd=0.65). They also disagree that implementing the competing strategy to manage organizational conflict would increase employee respect for management’s decisions leading to improved productivity in an organization as shown by the mean of 2.37 (sd=0.77). Majority of the respondents constituting 70.7% agree that management adopts the competing strategy to manage conflict within an organization for easy allocation of scarce resources as shown by the mean of 3.61 (sd=0.67), 75.8% of the respondents agree that organizations should adopt the competing strategy to manage conflict during emergencies as shown by the mean of 3.71 (sd=0.56). Salami, (2009) concurs with the above findings, stating that the competing approach is appropriate when quick, decisive action is needed such as during emergencies however, this study found that employees are less likely to cooperate when the competing strategy is used to manage organizational conflict evidenced by a 56.1% response rate where respondents disagreed with this statement as shown by the mean of 2.54 (sd=0.67) and they also strongly disagreed that implementing this strategy would improve the performance of NEPHAK as shown by the mean of 2.10 (sd=0.63).

Table 5: Means and Standard Deviations on Competing Strategy

Statement	Sample Size	Mean	Standard Deviation
Characterised by power dominance and coercion that is good for improving performance	41	2.07	0.65
Increases employee respect for management’s decisions leading to improved productivity	41	2.37	0.77
Adopted by management for easy allocation of scarce resources	41	3.61	0.67
Should be adopted during emergencies	41	3.71	0.56
Enhances employee cooperation	41	2.54	0.67
Leads to improved performance	41	2.10	0.63

Source: The Study, 2018

Avoiding Strategy

From the findings as presented in Table 6, it was established that the respondents are partial on whether adopting avoiding strategy would not increase productivity in an organization as shown by the mean of 2.05 (sd=0.74). However, the majority of the respondents disagreed with this statement. The respondents are of the opinion that organizations that adopt the avoiding strategy to manage conflict usually damage work relationships as shown by the mean of 4.20 (sd=0.87) and that this strategy promotes counterproductive work behaviour as shown by the mean of 4.27 (sd=0.78). The study further established that the avoiding strategy would not improve the performance as indicated by a mean of 1.98. Ogungbamila, (2006) confirmed these findings are arguing that avoiding conflict usually leaves those being avoided feeling neglected and usually fails to reconcile the perceived differences that originally caused the conflict.

Table 6: Means and Standard Deviations on Avoiding Strategy

Statement	Sample Size	Mean	Standard Deviation
Helps increase employee productivity	41	2.05	0.74
Damages work relationships	41	4.20	0.87
Promotes counterproductive work behaviour	41	4.27	0.78
Implementing the avoiding strategy would improve the performance of NEPHAK	41	1.98	0.82

Source: The Study, 2018

Organizational Performance

The findings as presented in Table 7 indicate that 61% of the respondents agreed that effective implementation of conflict management strategies leads to high productivity and improved staff morale and satisfaction in the organization as shown by the mean of 4.00 (sd=0.63). The respondents also agreed that organizations are able to achieve set goals and objectives when conflict management strategies are well selected and implemented as shown by the mean of 4.10 (sd=0.58) and conflict management strategies are poorly selected, it would lead to low staff retention and poor work attitudes as shown by the mean of 3.90 (sd=0.49). The study further established a majority of the respondent opined that selecting relevant conflict management strategies to specific conflict situations greatly affects effectiveness and efficiency in the overall organizational performance with 73.2% agreeing with the statement, as indicated by a mean of 4.02. Further, 75.6% of the respondents agreed that the overall work environment and organizational health that provides safety to employees is determined by selection and implementation of conflict management strategies as shown by a mean of 3.73 (sd=0.50).

Table 7: Means and Standard Deviations on Effects of CMS on Organizational Performance

Statement	Sample Size	Mean	Standard Deviation
High productivity, and improved staff morale and satisfaction in the organization	41	4.00	0.63
Achieve set goals and objectives	41	4.10	0.58
Poor selection leads to low staff retention and poor work attitudes	41	4.26	0.78
Affects effectiveness and efficiency in the overall organizational performance	41	4.02	0.52
Selection and implementation of conflict management strategies provide employee safety.	41	3.73	0.50

Source: The Study, 2018

4.3 Conflict Management Strategies Adopted by the Organization

The study sought to determine the challenges that were commonly experienced at NEPHAK while adopting conflict management strategies to improve performance. Means and standard deviation are used to interpret the research findings as provided by the respondents. Data presented in Table 8 indicates that struggle for scarce resources was the most common challenge for NEPHAK while adopting conflict management strategies, with a mean score of 4.34 (sd=0.64), meeting donor expectations were the second most challenging aspect with a mean of 4.26 (sd=0.72). The study also found that cultural differences were the third most common challenge when implementing conflict management strategies as indicated by a mean of 3.83 (sd=0.38). Differences in personality were fourth with a mean of 3.71 and incompatibility of goals came in fifth as indicated by a mean of 3.57 (sd=0.51).

Table 8: Means and Standard deviations of Challenges NEPHAK experienced while implementing Conflict Management Strategies

Conflict Management Strategy	Mean	Standard Deviation	Sample Size
Struggle for scarce resources	4.34	0.64	41
Incompatibility of goals	3.57	0.51	41
Cultural differences	3.83	0.38	41
Differences in personality	3.71	0.56	41
Meeting donor expectations	4.26	0.72	41

Source: The Study, 2018

4.4 Influence on Selection of Strategies by Senior Management

The study requested participants to indicate the extent to which senior management at NEPHAK influences the choice of conflict management strategies. From the findings as shown in Figure 4.6, 31.7% of the responses indicated that the senior management influenced the choice of conflict management strategies to a very large extent, while 68.3% indicated that they influence the selection of conflict management strategies to a great extent. Longe, (2015) confirms these findings as he also found that top management was mostly tasked with the responsibility of selecting conflict management strategies at the Nigerian manufacturing firm.

4.5 Test of Hypotheses

H0₁₋₅: There is no significant relationship between conflict management strategies (collaborating, compromising, accommodating, competing and avoiding) and the performance of NEPHAK.

Table 9 presents data showing that there is a significant relationship between conflict management strategies and organizational performance with the coefficient of 25.2% at the significance level of 0.01. The result reveals that the null hypothesis as suggested for the study was therefore rejected. From the test of hypotheses, a statistically significant relationship between conflict management strategies and organizational performance was found.

Table 9: Correlation Matrix

Conflict Management Strategies	Performance of NEPHAK	Variables
	1.000	Conflict Management Strategies
1.000	0.252** 0.01	Performance of NEPHAK

The correlation results presented in Table 10 indicate a positive relationship between collaborating strategy and organizational performance at the confidence level of 0.01 as indicated by Spearman’s correlation of 0.507 and thus the hypothesis about the collaborating strategy was rejected. Similarly, both compromising and accommodating strategies have a positive and significant correlation with organizational performance as indicated by Spearman’s correlation of 0.313 and 0.185. Consequently, the hypotheses that these strategies of

conflict management do not significantly enhance the performance of NEPHAK were also rejected. The strategies of competing and avoiding however indicated significantly negative correlations with the performance of NEPHAK as indicated by Spearman’s correlation of -0.034 and -0.097 respectively. Additionally, the results indicated a significant relationship as indicated by P-values of 0.000, 0.003, 0.003, 0.291 and 0.022 for the collaborating, compromising, accommodating, competing and avoiding strategies respectively.

Table 10: Correlation Matrix

Variables		COL	COM	ACC	COMP	AV	OP
COL	Spearman’s Correlation	1.000	0.000	0.051	0.456**	0.271	0.507**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		1.000	0.772	0.006	0.115	0.000
COM	Spearman’s Correlation	0.000	1.000	0.161	0.091	0.301	0.313**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	1.000		0.354	0.601	0.079	0.003
ACC	Spearman’s Correlation	0.051	0.161	1.000	0.024	0.052	0.185**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.772	0.114		0.893	0.766	0.003
COMP	Spearman’s Correlation	0.456**	0.220	0.024	1.000	0.069	-0.034**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.112	0.601	0.893		0.694	0.291
AV	Spearman’s Correlation	0.271	0.301	0.052	0.069	1.000	-0.097**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.115	0.079	0.766	0.694		0.022
OP	Spearman’s Correlation	0.507**	0.313**	0.185**	-0.034**	-0.097**	1.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.003	0.003	0.291	0.022	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

COL= Collaborating Strategy
 COM= Compromising Strategy
 4.6 Regression Analysis

ACC= Accommodating Strategy
 COMP= Compromising Strategy
 AV= Avoiding Strategy

The study conducted multiple regression analysis to determine the relationship between the independent and dependent variables as depicted in the conceptual framework. The established regression equation was:

$$Y_s = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + e$$

Where Ys = Dependent Variable (Organizational Performance)
 β_0 = constant coefficient
 X₁ = Collaborating strategy
 X₂ = Compromising strategy
 X₃ = Accommodating strategy
 X₄ = Competing strategy
 X₅ = Avoiding strategy
 e = error term

$\beta_1 - \beta_5$ = Regression coefficient of the five variables
 As shown in Table 11, the study found that there was a variation of 31.1% on the performance of NEPHAK due to collaborating, accommodating, compromising, competing and avoiding strategies at 95% confidence interval. This was determined by the Adjusted R squared, which is the coefficient of determination where (R²) was 0.397. This, therefore, means that the combined effects of the predictor variables (collaborating, accommodating, compromising, competing and avoiding strategies) explains 31.1% of the changes in organizational performance. This, therefore, indicates that other factors not studied in this research account for 68.9% of changes in organizational performance that needs further research to determine other factors that

affect organizational performance. The study also found that there was a strong positive relationship between the variables as shown by the strong correlation coefficient of (R) 0.630.

Table 11: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. The error of the Estimate
1	.630 ^a	0.397	0.311	0.580

Source: The Study, 2018

Analysis of Variance

The ANOVA statistics as presented in Table 12 established that the regression model had a significance level of 3% which is an indication that there is a 99.7% chance that there is a relationship between collaborating strategy, compromising strategy, accommodating strategy, competing strategies and avoiding strategy and performance. The calculated value (F=4.383 p<0.01) was greater than the critical F-value of 3.828. The significance value was less than 0.05 indicating that the model was statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance.

Table 12: Analysis of Variance

Model		Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F	Sig. ^b
1	Regression	7.532	1.506	4.383	0.03 ^b
	Residual	12.029	.344		
	Total	18.561			

Source: The Study, 2018

The overall model fit for regression equation as in Table 13 was determined by F-statistics. The model reveals a positive and statistically significant relationship (F = 4.383 P< 0.01). The predictor variables accounted for 39.6% (R² = 0.396) of the variance in the dependent variable of organizational performance. Collaborating conflict management strategy that had the highest beta -coefficient of (0.480) is the most effective, indicating a higher significant effect on performance, followed by compromising strategy (0.457), accommodating strategy (0.437), competing for strategy (0.210) and avoiding strategy (0.214) respectively.

This means that an increase in implementing the collaborating strategy, compromising strategy, accommodating strategy will positively increase organizational performance at 5% level of significance and 95% level of confidence. Since the t-calculated value was greater than the t-critical value for collaborating, compromising and accommodating, where t-cal = 2.775, 2.553, and 2.362 respectively > t-critical= 2.02, the null hypotheses were rejected, and the alternative is accepted that there is a significant relationship between collaborating, compromising and accommodating strategies with organizational performance. From the statistics, therefore, collaborating strategy had the greatest influence on performance followed by compromising strategy then accommodating strategy. The avoiding strategy had the least effect on the performance of NEPHAK. All variables were significant (p<0.05).

Table 13: Overall coefficient estimates of the variables

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error		
(Constant)	4.148	1.294	3.206	0.00
Collaborating strategy	0.480	0.173	2.775	0.000
Compromising strategy	0.457	0.179	2.553	0.000
Accommodating strategy	0.437	0.185	2.362	0.002
Avoiding strategy	0.214	0.175	1.223	0.032
Competing strategy	0.210	0.133	1.579	0.186

Significant level** p= 0.01 N=41

5. Research Summary

Findings from the study validated the assertions of Mba (2013) and Henry (2009) that managers prefer the use of integrative strategies to manage organizational conflict compared to the non-integrative conflict management strategies, since they are relatively useful in minimizing the incidence of disruptive conflict and having positive impact on corporate productivity and organizational performance (Longe, 2015).

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

The study highlighted the importance of adopting the collaborating strategy as a technique of preventing the destructive nature of a specific conflict situation in an organization to productive management of conflicts that enhance organizational performance. Reviewed literature provided further evidence that integrative conflict management strategies (collaborating, compromising and accommodating) are positively and significantly related to organizational performance. The study has greatly contributed to the understanding of the relationship between workplace conflict management and organizational performance specifically applicable to organizations that take up capacity building programs in the non-governmental sector.

The study recommends that:

1. Organizational managers should consider forming a task force that includes stakeholders from all cadres within the organizational structure that is charged with the responsibility of selecting appropriate conflict management strategies that the organization can adopt in case of emergencies.
2. Based on the findings of the study, management in the workplace should try to adopt inclusive and collaborative strategies and involve representatives from all cadres, especially when making important decisions that affect all members of the organization.
3. Management teams and employees should resolve to work together and harmoniously in order to formulate effective strategies to manage conflict within the organization and pro-actively include strategies to consider in case conflict arises in program implementation.
4. The study further recommends that organizations should also strive to sustain acceptable policies as effective tools to ensure continuous conflict management within the organization.
5. Organizational management should find credible channels of communication that encourage open discussions especially when conflict arises in work relations.
6. The management should also consider building conflict management skills through training to ensure employees have adequate knowledge in the application of conflict management strategies for diverse conflict situations.
7. Organizations should avoid adopting the non-integrative methods of competing and avoiding and adopt integrative methods such as collaborating, compromising and accommodating conflict management strategies.

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